

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Virtual EC2U Innovation Lecture Series: “Disrupt now?!: Views on Social, Economic and Technological Innovations” M24–M30–M36

DELIVERABLE 5.2
MONTH 36

D5.2 – Virtual Lecture Series *Innovation* M24-M30-M36

Table of contents

I.	General overview	3
A.	Summary	3
B.	The previous episodes (1-4).....	3
C.	Overview of episodes 5-7	7
II.	Feedback.....	10
III.	Promotion.....	11
IV.	Sustainability.....	12
V.	Annexes.....	13
A.	Selected examples - websites.....	13
B.	Selected examples – social media	15
C.	Feedback table	17

I. General overview

A. Summary

This deliverable addresses the last three episodes of the Virtual Lecture Series *Innovation*, which complements a Series of 7 lectures in total (see D5.1). This European lecture series encouraged a wide and critical understanding of innovation – from incremental to disruptive types of innovation, from technological to social innovations. It gave voice to various stakeholders from academia and industry within the innovation sphere that highlight different aspects of innovation. Topics so far include:

D5.1:

- Innovation and Uncertainty (University of Jena)
- Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship (University of Pavia)
- Social Innovation (University of Poitiers)
- Industry-University Collaboration (University of Turku)

D5.2:

- Strategic Innovation in Research (University of Coimbra)
- Innovation in Agriculture (University of Salamanca)
- Intangible Innovation: AI and Gamification in Education and Sustainability for Entrepreneurship (Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iasi)

The Virtual Lecture Series *Innovation* aimed at different target groups – interested citizens, students, and professionals from the university and industry. In total, the lecture series reached more than 10 000 views on YouTube.

B. The previous episodes (1-4)

These four lectures were part of the previous deliverable D5.1.

Date, time (CET), and platform	Host EC2U team	Episode Number and Title	Speaker	No of participants ¹
23.09.2021, 15:00-16:00 on Zoom	UJ	Episode 1: Innovation – so important but hard to predict or On how to outsmart uncertainty	Prof. Dr. Uwe Cantner , professor of microeconomics, Vice President for Young Researchers and Diversity Management at the University of Jena, and chairman of the Expert Commission on Research and Innovation (EFI) of the German federal government	22 live 470 views (137 views previously)
18.01.2022, 16:00-17:30 on Zoom	UNIPV	Episode 2: Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship	Beatrice Re , post-doctoral researcher at the University of Pavia Alberto Bressan as special guest, founder of the	96 live 238 views (146 views previously)

¹ Number of live participants plus number of views on YouTube by June 2024 (and previously by January 2023).

			circular fashion company SEAY	
15.6.2022, 15:00-17:00 on YouTube	UP	Episode 3: Social Innovation: The dynamics of companies, society and territories towards social innovations	Prof. Dominique Royoux , professor of geography and Co-Chairman of the Joint Research Unit "DESTINS" Ursula Dechein , research engineer at "DESTINS" and Sébastien Palluault , Co-funder of the Company "Ellyx" and Member of the Executive Committee of "DESTINS"	20 live 244 views (188 views previously)
13.12.2022, 10:00-11:00 on Zoom	UTU	Episode 4: A new level in industry-university collaboration: The Entrepreneurs in Residence (EiR) programme at the University of Turku	Laura Strömberg , Founder and CEO of Dagsmark Petfood, EiR. Jussi Karttila , Founder and CEO of Zefort, EiR. Jarna Heinonen , Professor of Entrepreneurship.	20 live 47 views

			<p>Sanna Ilonen, University teacher in Entrepreneurship</p>	
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Figure 1: Key visuals of the first four episodes

C. Overview of episodes 5-7

Date, time (CET), and platform	Host EC2U team	Episode Number and Title	Speaker	No of participants ²
30.06.2023 14:00-15:00 CEST on Zoom	UC	Episode 5: Innovative Strategies for the Development of New Research Ideas	Jorge Noro, Executive Coordinator of Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of University of Coimbra. Ana Santos Carvalho, Science Communication Coordinator at Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of University of Coimbra.	9 live 8424 views
23.11.2023 11:30-13:00 CET on Zoom	USAL	Episode 6: Innovation in Agriculture. Agriculture 4.0.	Diego González-Aguilera, Professor of Engineering at the University of Salamanca and Director of the	5 live 3797 views

² Number of live participants plus number of views on Youtube by June 2024.

			<p>TIDOP Research Unit.</p> <p>Luis Enrique Corredera, Director of Innovation and Digital Transformation at Deloitte.</p> <p>Raúl García Serrada, Project Manager at the Air Institute USAL.</p> <p>Óscar Lorenzo, Rector's Delegate for Transfer and Innovation and Professor of Botany at the University of Salamanca.</p>	
<p>25.06.2024 13:00-14:30 CEST on Webex</p>	UAIC	<p>Episode 7: Intangible Innovation - AI and gamification for education and sustainability for entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Catalin Vrabie, Associate Professor at National University of Political Studies and Public Administration Bucharest.</p> <p>Valentina Diana Rusu, Senior Researcher at</p>	14 live

				Institute for Interdisciplinary Research, Social Sciences and Humanities, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iași.
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The Lecture Series is available on [Youtube](#).

Figure 2: Key visuals of the last three episodes

Figure 3: Exemplary visual impression of the series on YouTube

II. Feedback

At the end of every episode, the audience was asked to fill in a feedback survey. In total, 15 feedback answers were submitted (see Annex). In average, 4.8 stars out of 5 stars were given. All answers had 4 or 5 stars, which shows the high satisfaction rate.

III. Promotion

All episodes were promoted through various channels. Each Virtual Lecture on Innovation (VLS) was featured on ec2u.eu with a dedicated news page. In addition, some local university websites listed it as an event. Social media platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram) were used—not only by the official EC2U account, but also by the universities, board members, and city communities who promoted the event via their networks. Please see the Annexes for some examples.

Figure 4: Collage of announcements

As before, each lecture has its own key visual in a similar design: an illustration on a light blue background, with dotted yellow line, and people interacting with one symbol (e.g., arrows, plant, cloud, etc). The people illustrations are designed by Pablo Stanley (CC0 license), and the overall collage was created by Eleonore Roderfeld, according to the topic of the lecture.

IV. Sustainability

Besides being a one-time event, the lecture series aims to have a sustainable impact. The recordings will be available online for all interested people and can be referred to in other EC2U activities, like the Think Tanks or the Entrepreneurial Academy. The insights provided by the lectures will also contribute to a Best Practice exchange between the EC2U cities and innovation actors.

V. Annexes

A. Selected examples - websites

Latest News

RI4C2 NEWS

Follow-up to the kick-off event of the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem!

NEWS

Intangible innovation completes the Virtual Lecture Series

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[EC2U](#) > [Events and news](#) > [Intangible innovation completes the Virtual Lecture Series](#)

Intangible innovation completes the Virtual Lecture Series

🕒 Temps de lecture : 2 minutes

Share on Facebook

Share on Twitter

For the upcoming episode of the Virtual Lecture Series, the focus will be on intangible innovation from two perspectives: AI and gamification for education and sustainability for entrepreneurship. This 7th and final episode will be hosted by the Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iași. You are warmly invited to join virtually on June 25th at 13:00 CEST!

"Education 3.0 – AI and gamification tools for increasing student engagement and knowledge retention"

by Catalin Vrabie, Associate Professor at National University of Political Studies and Public Administration Bucharest.

The presentation explores the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and gamification in education to enhance student engagement and retention of knowledge. It presents a framework based on literature and institutional research, discussing a pilot project where a computer science course was redesigned using these technologies. The study compares the academic performance of two student groups: one taught with traditional e-learning methods and the other with AI and gamification-enhanced tools. The results show improved academic performance and satisfaction in the group using the innovative methods, suggesting that AI and gamification can significantly enhance learning experiences.

"Being a sustainable entrepreneurs as pillar of innovation"

by Valentina Diana Rusu, Senior Researcher at Institute for Interdisciplinary Research, Social Sciences and Humanities, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iași.

Sustainable entrepreneurs apply in their activity innovative thinking and business strategies and try to solve issues taking into account the environment, community and the society. By tackling environmental and social problems head-on, sustainable entrepreneurs often develop pioneering technologies and business models. Thus being considered as pillars of innovation.

Figure 5: VLS7 invitation on www.ec2u.eu

Figure 6: VLS6 event invitation on the USAL website

EVENT DETAILS	
Start	30 June 2023, 14:00
End	30 June 2023, 15:00
Type of event	EC2U
Video chat	Zoom – Video chat ^{RP}
	Data protection information ^{RP} PDF, 101 KB
Livestream	Go to the YouTube livestream ^{RP}
Organizer	EC2U-Allianz

Figure 7: VLS5 event invitation in German, on the website of the University of Jena

B. Selected examples – social media

Beitrag von III_UC | Institute of Interdisciplinary Research

EC2U Alliance
1.398 Follower:innen
6 Tage · Bearbeitet

Join us for the 7th & final episode of the Virtual Lecture Series hosted by Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași!

Topic: **Intangible Innovation**
 #AI & #Gamification for Education
 #Sustainability for #Entrepreneurship

June 25th
13:00 CEST

Don't miss out! <https://lnkd.in/euKk8nEk>

Université de Poitiers | Universidad de Salamanca | Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena | Universidade de Coimbra | Università di Pavia | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku | Johannes Kepler University

Virtual Lecture Series *Innovation*
25 June 2024
 13:00-15:00 CEST
Intangible innovation
 Catalin Vrabie
 National University of Political Studies and Public Administration Bucharest
 Valentina Diana Rusu
 Institute for Interdisciplinary Research,
 Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iași

24 · 1 Kommentar

III_UC | Institute of Interdisciplinary Research
1.056 Follower:innen
1 Jahr

[Reminder: RI4C2 | Virtual Lecture Series]

Don't miss, on June 30, from 13:00 to 14:00 GMT (14:00 - 15:00 CET), the 5th episode of the cycle of conferences of the RI4C2 project "Research and Innovation for Cities and Citizens", hosted by the Universidade de Coimbra through III_UC | Institute of Interdisciplinary Research.

In this episode, we will debate with the EC2U community "Innovative strategies for the development of new research ideas".

We will address topics such as the promotion of interdisciplinary collaboration, digital platforms to support research and alternative ways to share research results.

Topics such as fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, digital research support platforms, and alternative ways to share research results will be addressed.

The session is open to the whole EC2U community via the zoom link: <https://lnkd.in/d-TjkAQ2>

You can also watch it on the Youtube Channel of the EC2U Alliance or on the Youtube channel of the Institute for Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra (iiiuc).

Don't miss this opportunity to learn more about these essential topics!

#EC2U #ri4c2 #iiiuc #research #UCoimbra

University of Poitiers | Friedrich Schiller University Jena | Università di Pavia | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku | Universidade de Coimbra | Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași | Universidad de Salamanca | EC2U Alliance

Virtual Lecture Series *Innovation*
30 June 2023
 14:00-15:00 CET
 13:00-14:00 GMT
Innovative Strategies for the Development of New Research Ideas
 Jorge Noro & Ana dos Santos Carvalho

5

Figure 8: VLS7 and VLS5 invitations by EC2U and III_UC account on LinkedIn

EC2U Alliance
30. Juni 2023 · 🌐

[🔴 #ri4c2 live]

The Virtual Lecture Series on Innovation hosted by **Universidade de Coimbra** starts in a few minutes...

Join us 📺 <https://www.youtube.com/@ec2ualliance31/featured>

Virtual Lecture Series Innovation
30 June 2023
14:00-15:00 CET

Innovative Strategies for the Development of **New Research Ideas**

Jorge Noro & Ana dos Santos Carvalho

EC2U Alliance
23. Juni 2023 · 🌐

A new episode of the **Virtual Lecture Series on Innovation** will be broadcasted next week! 🌟

Follow this new lecture on "Innovative Strategies for the Development of New Research Ideas"

June 30th, 14:00 CET

Researchers and PhD students: seize this opportunity to explore complementary alternatives to your training, discover ways to share your results with the public, and expand your network by fostering the development of fresh research ideas.

Speakers:

- Jorge Noro – Executive Coordinator of Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of **Universidade de Coimbra**
- Ana Santos Carvalho – Science Communication Coordinator at Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of **Universidade de Coimbra**

Join the live session on the EC2U YouTube channel:
<https://www.youtube.com/@ec2ualliance31>

Let's innovate together and shape the future of research! 🚀

#EC2U #research #innovation #lectureseries #virtualevent #ri4c2

Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași | Universidade de Coimbra | Università degli studi di Pavia | Universität Jena | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku | Université de Poitiers | Universidad de Salamanca

EC2U Alliance
16. November 2023 · 🌐

The 6th episode of the #ri4c2 Virtual Lecture Series will engage with the EC2U community to discuss "Innovation in Agriculture: Agriculture 4.0"

When? On November, the 23th – 11:30am CET

Where? <https://usal-es.zoom.us/j/89358762118> (code RI4C2)

More info <https://eventos.usal.es/.../virtual-lecture-series...>

Universidade de Coimbra | Università degli studi di Pavia | Turun yliopisto - University of Turku | Universität Jena | Université de Poitiers | Universidad de Salamanca | Universitatea „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” din Iași

Virtual Lecture Series Innovation
23 November 2023
11:30-13:00 CET

Innovation in agriculture
Agriculture 4.0

Diego González Aguilera (TIDOP, USAL)
Luis Enrique Corredera (Consultant)
Raúl García Serrada (AIR Institute, USAL)
Oscar Lorenzo (Transfer and Innovation, USAL)

Yolanda Voda mit Adriana Zait und 2 weiteren Personen ...
18. Juni um 05:42 · 🌐

#RI4C2 #InnovationSeries

The 7th and final episode of the Virtual Lectures Series will be hosted by the Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iași. You are warmly invited to join virtually on June 25th at 13:00 CEST!

How to attend?

The lecture is held in English and open to the public. You are invited to join on June 25th 2024 at 13:00 CEST (14:00 Iași- and Turku-time, 12:00 Coimbra-time) <https://uaic.webex.com/uaic/j.php...>

Virtual Lecture Series Innovation
25 June 2024
13:00-15:00 CEST

Intangible innovation

Catalin Vrabie
National University of Political Studies and Public Administration Bucharest

Valentina Diana Rusu
Institute for Interdisciplinary Research, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iași

Figure 9: Invitations for VLS5, VLS6 and VLS7 on Facebook

C. Feedback table

E: Number of episodes

Star: Number of stars in a 5-star rating system

E	★	What could be improved?	What topics would you like to see in the following episodes?	Background
5	5			Student
5	5			Professional (at university)
5	5	n. a.	Research Integrity	Professional (at university)
5	4			Student
5	4	Greater publicity for the event to attract more participants	Technology transfer and/or intellectual property; Career paths in Science and Technology	Professional (at university)
5	5	Audio quality and internet connection was a bit weak. The examples presented were quite interesting though.		Professional (at university)
5	4	More examples	How can people be trained to be less change resistant and more innovative	Professional (at university)
7	5		Transfer of knowledge and technology	Student
7	5	NA	AI and ML	Professional (at university)
7	5			Professional (at university)
7	5			Professional (at university)
7	5	Maybe the sound?	Research policy, innovation projects and funding	Professional (at university)
7	5	Nothing to mention	I have two questions in mind: How will AI and machine learning reshape industries in the next decade? What ethical	Professional (at university)

			considerations arise from the widespread use of AI?	
7	5	The moderation after the first lecture could be better	I don't know	Student
7	5	Better anticipate the digital format and its technical requirements to avoid issues with the sharing of screens etc...		Professional (at university)

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